

Ileocolic Volvulus: A Rare Complication of Chilaiditi Syndrome

A. Ettaoussi, K. Jamaledine ✉, C. Bukaka, K. Kamal, A. Majd, M. Bouali, A. El Bakkouri, K. Elhattabi, F.Z. Bensardi, A. Fadil

Visceral surgical emergency department, IBN ROCHD University hospital of Casablanca, Casablanca, Morocco

Abstract

Chilaiditi's syndrome is a rare condition where a segment of the digestive tract becomes trapped between the liver and the diaphragm, often without symptoms, making diagnosis challenging. However, it can lead to severe complications such as abdominal pain, bowel obstruction, or even perforation, necessitating prompt medical attention. In the presented case, a 54-year-old man with a significant surgical history developed acute abdominal pain due to this syndrome, leading to necrosis and perforation of an old intestinal anastomosis. Imaging confirmed the diagnosis, and surgery was required to resect the affected area. The condition has a low global incidence and primarily affects elderly males, with diagnosis relying heavily on imaging techniques like abdominal CT and chest X-ray to differentiate it from other critical conditions.

Introduction

Chilaiditi syndrome is a rare and often unknown condition among some healthcare professionals, characterized by the interposition of a segment of the gastrointestinal tract between the liver and the hemidiaphragm. [3] This interposition can sometimes be asymptomatic, making it easy to miss the diagnosis. When symptomatic (gastrointestinal symptoms), clinical examination is always complemented by imaging, leading to the diagnosis. [4]

Chilaiditi syndrome can be accompanied by certain complications, particularly those related to the incarcerated bowel segment, such as obstructive syndrome, volvulus, and digestive perforation. Volvulus most often occurs in a part of the colon, but it can occur in any part of the digestive tract, including the stomach, gallbladder, and small intestine. According to the literature, the most frequent sites are the sigmoid colon and cecum, with the transverse colon and splenic flexure being less common. [8]

Aim of the Article

The objective of our article is to raise awareness about the possibility that an anastomosis volvulus can occur

in chilaiditi, presenting various types of complications, and to identify the potential causes of this condition.

Presentation of Case

We present a 54-year-old man with a history of appendectomy in 2016 via McBurney's incision and resection of 1 meter of the ileum combined with a segmental colectomy (cecum + ascending colon) for acute intestinal obstruction (neglected adhesion) with ileocolic anastomosis in 2019. He presented to the emergency department with generalized abdominal pain lasting 4 days, associated with an obstructive syndrome characterized by cessation of bowel movements and gas, with vomiting but without gastrointestinal bleeding or respiratory distress; all in a context of afebrile condition and general deterioration characterized by unquantified weight loss.

On physical examination, the patient was conscious with a correct Glasgow score, stable hemodynamically and respiratorily, afebrile on palpation, and the rest of the general examination was unremarkable.

Abdominal examination revealed a median laparotomy scar above and below the umbilicus and a McBurney scar. The abdomen was non-distended, tympanic, and

More Information

How to cite this article: Ettaoussi A, Jamaledine K, Bukaka C, Kamal K, Majd A, Bouali M, El Bakkouri A, Elhattabi K, Bensardi FZ, Fadil A. Ileocolic Volvulus: A Rare Complication of Chilaiditi Syndrome. Eur J Med Health Res, 2024;2(6):39-43.

DOI: 10.59324/ejmhr.2024.2(6).05

Keywords:

Chilaiditi, ileocolic volvulus, volvulus, necrosis, resection.

This work is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License. The license permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, on the condition that users give exact credit to the original author(s) and the source, provide a link to the Creative Commons license, and indicate if they made any changes.

diffusely tender. Hernial areas were unremarkable, and no palpable abdominal masses were detected. The rectal examination was unremarkable.

The pulmonary examination did not reveal any particular findings that would suggest a diagnosis; pulmonary expansion was satisfactory, the vesicular murmur was clear, and vocal transmission was unobstructed.

An abdominal-pelvic CT scan performed with helical multi-planar acquisition without IV contrast showed

moderate pneumoperitoneum, significant infiltration of the right flank with moderate peritoneal effusion in the right parietal-colic gutter and pelvic area, associated with an irregular and thickened appearance of the lower cecal wall; significant distension of the right colon pushing the liver, with hydro-aeric levels, and thickening of the last ileal loop with significant distension of other ileal loops measuring up to 36 mm.

Figure 1: CT Scan Appearance of a Hollow Organ Perforation with Moderate Pneumoperitoneum and Moderate Peritoneal Effusion

The patient was quickly taken to the operating room. The surgery consisted of resecting the volvulized, necrotic, and perforated old ileocolic anastomosis in Chilaiditi syndrome, performing a double-barreled ileocolostomy, peritoneal lavage with saline, and draining the Douglas pouch with a Salem sump tube. Exploration findings:

- Presence of a large peritoneal effusion consisting of hemoperitoneum (sampled and evacuated).
- Presence of the old ileocolic anastomosis in Chilaiditi syndrome, volvulized with a counter-clockwise twist, necrotic and perforated 3.80 meters from the duodenojejunal junction (Figure 2).

- Stomach, antrum-pyloric region, liver, gallbladder, and the rest of the exploration were unremarkable.

- Posterior aspect of the stomach was unremarkable.

Figure 2: Old Ileocolic Anastomosis in Chilaiditi Syndrome with Volvulus

Figure 3: Surgical Specimen

Postoperative recovery was straightforward. Therapeutically, the patient was given analgesics, antibiotics, and preventive heparin therapy. The Salem sump tube from the Douglas pouch was removed on the fourth postoperative day, and the patient was discharged on postoperative day 6.

Discussion

The hepatodiaphragmatic interposition of the colon, known as Chilaiditi syndrome, is generally an incidental finding. Usually asymptomatic, Chilaiditi syndrome can cause intermittent or persistent symptoms related to bowel obstruction. [1] If the patient is symptomatic, it is referred to as Chilaiditi syndrome, which can manifest as abdominal pain, constipation, nausea or vomiting, and even dyspnea. It can be complicated by obstruction, volvulus, or gastrointestinal perforation. Diagnosis is made using chest radiography and abdominal CT scans. [2]

This syndrome was first defined in 1910 by Demetrius Chilaiditi, a Greek radiologist, after he reported three cases of patients whose radiological imaging revealed the presence of free intra-abdominal air caused by the interposition of the intestine between the right hemidiaphragm and the liver. The Chilaiditi sign has an incidence of 0.025% to 0.28% worldwide, with a male-to-female ratio of 4:1. It occurs most frequently in the elderly, with an incidence of 1%. [6]

Typically, the part of the intestine that most often interposes is the hepatic flexure, the ascending colon, or the transverse colon, but cases involving the small intestine have been reported. In our case, it was the ileocolic anastomosis that had volvulized in the context of Chilaiditi syndrome. No similar case has been reported in a scientific review in the last 20 years. In 2021, L. Kallouch et al. published that the sigmoid colon is most often twisted due to its anatomical structure (60-80% of cases), followed by the cecum (20-40%). [8] The volvulus can affect a fixed part of the colon, which, theoretically, cannot move due to its retroperitoneal location, fixation by various ligaments, or a wide mesenteric attachment base. Cases of Chilaiditi syndrome associated with volvulus of the cecum, transverse colon, and splenic flexure of the colon have been reported. [8]

Cases of simultaneous volvulus of the transverse colon and another colonic segment are rare. Published literature on the epidemiology of patients with colonic volvulus reveals that it is more common in elderly men (>70 years), people of African descent, and patients with diabetes mellitus and neuropsychiatric disorders. [8]

The association between transverse colon volvulus and Chilaiditi syndrome is also a well-documented issue. Volvulus on anastomosis is still a poorly understood entity regarding its mechanism of occurrence. The most

common and feared complication of an ileocolic anastomosis remains an anastomotic fistula, whose wide incidence variation (1-15.9%) partially depends on the height of the anastomosis, with risk factors including diabetes, hypoalbuminemia, smoking, and location at the right colic angle. [7] The majority of authors have discussed Chilaiditi syndrome associated with various complications of the interposed segment, but volvulus on anastomosis in Chilaiditi has not been mentioned. In this context, we conduct this work to raise awareness of the existence of such cases.

No specific patient history can explain the mode of onset of the volvulized anastomosis; its incidental and unprecedented discovery initiates a series of ongoing research. An abdominal CT scan is recommended to confirm the presence of free air (which would indicate surgical intervention) compared to Chilaiditi syndrome, which would be managed conservatively. [6] However, surgery is indicated for those who do not respond to conservative management or in cases of suspected severe complications such as intestinal ischemia or perforation. [5] In our case, the patient had already presented with advanced complications necessitating surgical intervention.

Conclusion

Chilaiditi syndrome remains a rare pathology that requires a well-conducted clinical examination. The colon and its segments are the predominant sites in Chilaiditi syndrome, with the possibility of causing a volvulus. The presence of a volvulized anastomosis on Chilaiditi syndrome is an extremely rare occurrence, necessitating a meticulous case study approach. Chilaiditi syndrome predominantly affects the elderly, and imaging techniques such as thoracoabdominal CT scans or chest radiography are crucial for diagnosis, especially when there is a divergence between anatomical landmarks and clinical presentation.

Provenance and Peer Review:

Not commissioned, externally peer reviewed.

Consent

As per international standard or university standard, patient(s) written consent has been collected and preserved by the author(s).

Ethical Approval

As per international standard or university standard written ethical approval has been collected and preserved by the author(s).

Conflicts Interests

Authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Source of Funding

None

References

[1] Barroso JM, Corrêa EP, Lopes TL, Araujo SA, Matos D. Chilaiditi syndrome associated with

transverse colon volvulus: first report in a pediatric patient and review of the literature. *Eur J Pediatr Surg.* 2003;13(6):418-421. doi:10.1055/s-2003-44709.

[2] Glatre A, Mahmoudi R. Syndrome de Chilaiditi. *Rev Med Interne.* 2022;43(1):66-70. doi:10.1016/j.revmed.2021.07.130.

[3] Plorde JJ, Raker EJ. Transverse colon volvulus and associated Chilaiditi's syndrome: case report and literature review. *Am J Gastroenterol.* 1996 Dec;91(12):2613-2616.

[4] Laquière A, Palazzo L. Colonic volvulus associated with Chilaiditi's syndrome: report of a case. *Surg Today.* 2004;34(3):265-267. doi:10.1007/s00595-003-2688-7.

[5] Kao CT, Hsieh CF, Lee LT. Surgical management of large bowel obstruction and significant hepatic displacement caused by Chilaiditi syndrome. *BMJ Case Rep.* 2023; doi:10.1136/bcr-2022-253837.

[6] Kumar A, Mehta D. Chilaiditi syndrome. *BMJ Case Rep.* 2023 Apr 10; doi:10.1136/bcr-2023-255061.

[7] Golda T, Lazzara C, Martin CZ, Roncero LS, Fico V, Moreno EK, Biondo S. Risk factors for ileocolic anastomosis dehiscence: a cohort study. 2019.

[8] Kallouch L, Jroundi L, Laamrani FZ. A very rare case of synchronous volvulus of the transverse colon and sigmoid causing large-bowel obstruction. Department of Emergency Radiology, (CHU) Ibn Sina, Rabat, Morocco. 2008.

